

5th Generation connected and automated mobility cross-border EU trials (5G-ROUTES)

D6.4 Project Website and Social Media Presence

Document Summary Information

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Glossary of terms and abbreviations used

Abbreviation / Term	Description
DEC	Websites, patent fillings, videos, etc. (Deliverable Type)
DoA	Description of Actions
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GUI	Graphical User Interface
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
KOM	Kick Off Meeting
M	Month (Project Month)
PU	Public (Dissemination Level)
T	Task (Project Task)
WP	Work Package

1 Executive Summary

This deliverable is part of WP6 ‘Dissemination, Communication and scale-up’, and supports the work under Task T6.1 “Dissemination and communication activities” with the creation, development and constant update of all web-based communication means, including the project’s website and social media channels.

The current document provides a detailed description and analysis of the project’s website and social media accounts, considered as the online Project’ presence.

Regarding the online presence, the project website has been created and will be maintained by EBOS in order to:

- Promote the project’s public image and serve as the main online access point for the different target groups;
- Serve as an information source, highlighting project objectives, activities, outcomes and relevant updates;
- Serve as a repository of information.

The methodology behind the design and implementation of a dynamic, modern and user-friendly website with multi-browser and multi-device compatibility, is described in this document. The first version of the website is ready and publicly available at www.5g-routes.eu. In addition, the administration of the website is also described in this document along with Google Analytics presenting the website’s traffic. The website also has a restricted area, only accessible (via login) by project partners, the EC Project Scientific Officer and the project’s review panel team. This restricted area may contain documents and confidential information related to the project’s internal activities and reporting.

Regarding the social media, 5G-ROUTES will use Twitter, LinkedIn, YouTube, as a two-way access between the project partners, the technical and the public audience. The consortium will regularly publish announcements and initiate discussions from month M06. Access to the social media accounts is also provided through this document. LinkedIn, Twitter and YouTube accounts have already been setup and are accessible via the following links:

- <https://twitter.com/5gRoutes>
- <https://www.linkedin.com/company/5g-routes-project/>
- <https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCEvuQqzJPpMYQdQPvQ1dD4g/>

The content of the website and the social media accounts will be continuously updated with dissemination materials (i.e. meetings, publications, results, etc.) until the completion of the Project.

All the above-mentioned links, have already been provided to the Consortium via invitations and also during the Kick Off Meeting (KOM).

2 Introduction

The deliverable “D6.4 Project Website and Social Media Presence” of 5G-ROUTES project is part of WP6 “Dissemination, communication and scale-up” and it refers to the design, development and publishing of the project’s official website as well as the setup of other social media channels, such as LinkedIn¹ and Twitter².

The deliverable is of significant importance since it marks from an early stage the “online” dissemination activity and the initial web presence and visibility of 5G-ROUTES project. The first website version was set-up during M1 (September 2020) and will be continuously updated until the end of the project.

2.1 Mapping 5G-ROUTES Outputs

The purpose of this section, is to map 5G-ROUTES’s Grand Agreement (GA) commitments, both within the formal Deliverable and Task description, against the project’s respective outputs and work performed.

Table 1: Adherence to 5G-ROUTES’s GA Deliverable & Tasks Descriptions

5G-ROUTES GA Component Title	5G-ROUTES GA Component Outline	Respective Document Chapter(s)	Justification
TASKS			
Task T6.1 - Dissemination and communication activities (Leader: CTTC)	Communication media [CTTC]: Ensure the creation and constant update of all web-based communication means, including the project’s website (from M01 by EBOS), as outlined in Section 2.2.1.2 of the DoA.	Chapter 3, 4 and Annex 1	Description and screenshots from the Project’s website and social media accounts. Methodology followed during the website design and implementation. The administration of the website, and Google Analytics showing the website traffic.
DELIVERABLE			
D6.4: Project Website and Social Media Presence			
Creation, development and constant update of all web-based communication means, including the project’s website and social media channels.			

2.2 Deliverable Overview and Report Structure

Based on the objectives and work carried out under task T6.1, the document starts with the Executive Summary in Chapter1 followed by the introduction of the document in Chapter 2. Chapter 3, provides an extensive description of the project’s website including the development methodology used along with content and

¹ <https://www.linkedin.com/>

² <https://twitter.com/>

screenshots for each page. Chapter 3 also provides some Google Analytics results for the website along with a description on how the administration of the website can be performed (i.e. update content, add-remove pages, etc.). Chapter 4, includes the relevant information about social media accounts of the project and Chapter 5 presents the conclusions. Finally, Annex 1 provides screenshots from all the pages of the website.

3 Project's Website

This Chapter describes in detail the 5G-ROUTES website that has been developed to serve as the public presence of the Project. It is a website that utilizes the latest technology in order to deliver content rich information to the visitor. The 5G-ROUTES website is part of the dissemination activities undertaken for this project. The Project website can be accessed using the following internet address www.5g-routes.eu.

3.1 Methodology for website construction and development

For the design and implementation of 5G-ROUTES's official website, the user interface design principles and user experience have been taken into consideration. 5G-ROUTES modern interface uses the latest technology to achieve multi-browser and multi-device compatibility. Further to that, 5G-ROUTES interface is fully responsive; user friendly; enables the user experience and delivers content rich information to the visitor. That means that the user is able to access 5G-ROUTES website from smartphone, tablet, desktop PC or laptop and have an easy access to the content. Both the design and implementation process follow a user-centered implementation, to build an interface that is efficient and easy to use.

Furthermore, the following GUI Design Principles³ were adapted in 5G-ROUTES website interface design and implementation:

- **Clarity:** The interface is visually, conceptually and linguistically clear;
- **Comprehensibility:** The interface is easily understood and flow easily to be learned;
- **Consistency:** The interface look, acts, and operates the same throughout;
- **Control:** The user controls the interaction;
 - Actions results from explicit user requests;
 - Actions are performed quickly;
 - Actions are capable of interruption or termination;
 - The user is never interrupted for errors;
- **Efficiency:**
 - Minimize user's eye and hand movements;
 - Transitions between various system controls flows easily and freely;
 - Navigation paths are as short as possible. Ensure that users never lose their work as a result of an error on their part;
- **Simplicity:**
 - Provide an interface as simple as possible;
 - Make common actions simple;
 - Provide uniformity and consistency.

Technologies of HTML5⁴, CSS3⁵ and JavaScript⁶ adopted during the implementation of 5G-ROUTES interface, in order to archive the responsive result, cross browser and multi device compatibility. Figure 1 below presents how the website looks like when using a smartphone.

³ https://en.wikibooks.org/wiki/GUI_Design_Principles

⁴ https://www.w3schools.com/html/html5_intro.asp

⁵ https://www.w3schools.com/css/css3_intro.asp

⁶ <https://www.w3schools.com/js/>

Figure 1: 5G-ROUTES Website – Smartphone View

3.2 Website content and screenshots

For producing the website structure, the mapping tool called SlickPlan⁷ was used. The following Figure shows in a diagram the sitemap of the initial working version of 5G-ROUTES website.

Figure 2: 5G-ROUTES Website Structure

⁷ <https://slickplan.com/>

The “Home” page of 5G-ROUTES website is the one loaded first when the user enters the 5G-ROUTES website in a web browser. Screenshots from the “Home” page of the website are shown in Figures 3 to 5 below.

Figure 3: 5G-ROUTES Website – Home Page 1/3

Objectives

- 1** Innovative use cases defined with key industry experts: To develop innovative and commercially exploitable CAM use cases for automotive, railway and maritime sectors within the cross-border context.
- 2** Requirements analysis elaboration: To analyse the technical and business requirements for the use cases to enable extensive large-scale CAM field trials in the 'Via Baltica-North' 5G corridor.
- 3** Enabling Technologies: To advance and optimise the enabling technologies using AI for the reliable, seamless and uninterrupted delivery of interoperable CAM services across borders.
- 4** Infrastructure development, integration & setup: To leverage and upgrade key assets from previous results and commercial products; to integrate the technological enablers in an end-to-end CAM ecosystem, to setup the 5G corridor and to facilitate lab and large-scale field trial validation.
- 5** Field Trials Validation: To demonstrate the potential and the user value in advanced CAM deployments at cross-border areas, by characterising and optimising 5G technologies at both lab tests and large-scale trials, so as to validate applicable standards and key target KPIs thus boosting the confidence for wide adoption of interoperable CAM services in Europe.
- 6** Exploitation & Innovation Management: To develop and validate the business models of advanced CAM use cases that can be offered on top of existing services in a multi cross-border 5G operator environment, demonstrating benefits from potential operational cost reductions and new revenue generation streams. To protect EU IP and ensure long-term economic sustainability.
- 7** Contribution to Standardisation: To identify and validate applicable standards as well as provide rationalised contribution to key standardisation bodies so as to sustain standardisation in the telecom and automotive sectors within the CAM context.
- 8** Scale-up: To ensure long-term success through wide dissemination of the project's results; to exploit synergies with other 5G-PPP projects and 5G CAM initiatives; to actively contribute to the 5G Action Plan strategic initiative with results from 5G technologies validation in CAM trials for the benefit of the European 5G, automotive, railways, maritime, transport & logistics industries, the university education and training of young and other professionals.

Subscribe to our newsletter

Subscribe

Figure 4: 5G-ROUTES Website – Home Page 2/3

Figure 5: 5G-ROUTES Website – Home Page 3/3

As seen in the Figures above, the “Home” page includes a header that hosts links to all social media of 5G-ROUTES Project in LinkedIn and Twitter. The “Header” section has been designed in a way that guides the user to navigate within the website, that’s why it is accessible from all the pages. Within the “Header” the project Logo is displayed and when pressed it redirects the user to the home page.

Furthermore, the “Home” page includes a background picture relevant to the Project, focusing on what the Project is about along with a central button that leads the visitor to read more information about it. Below that, the “Home” page includes separate links with the appropriate design that redirects the user to the vertical industries that are covered in the Project. There is also a “News and Events” section, which is linked with the Project Twitter and automatically presented tweets posted there.

Screenshots from the rest of the pages (as listed in the diagram of Figure 2), can be found in Annex 1 “Project’s Website Pages”, presenting information about the Project (i.e. consortium, objectives, work plan, etc.), dissemination and communication material (i.e. public deliverables, workshops, newsletters, etc.), news and events along with contact information.

An “Accept Cookies” option is also available when loading the website for the first time (Figure 6), and options can be modified as shown at any time (Figures 7, 8). Terms of Service and Privacy Policy are in align with the

General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and publicly available in the following URLs and accessible from the Home page.

- <https://www.5g-routes.eu/terms-of-service/>
- <https://www.5g-routes.eu/privacy-policy/>

Figure 6: 5G-ROUTES Website – Accept Cookies

Figure 7: 5G-ROUTES Website – Change Cookie Settings 1/2

Figure 8: 5G-ROUTES Website – Change Cookie Settings 2/2

The website also has a restricted members area⁸, only accessible via login (passwords will be provided via email) to project partners, the EC project scientific officer and the project review panel team. This restricted area might contain documents and confidential information related to the project’s internal activities and reporting.

⁸ <https://www.5g-routes.eu/members-area/>

3.3 Google Analytics Website Traffic

Google Analytics⁹ is a free web analytics service offered by Google that tracks the website traffic and reports through Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) the results. 5G-ROUTES website is registered in Google Analytics which offers a vast amount of reports to satisfy even the more demanding web masters. Below sample screenshots with analytics results are listed, as they have been generated for the first month of the project, presenting an audience overview information like:

- Number of sessions, users and page views;
- Average session duration and percentage of new sessions;
- Demographic statistics (e.g. sessions per country);
- Users that accessed the webpage using different devices (desktop and mobile);
- Active users (real-time, by time of day, etc.).

Figure 9: Google Analytics 1/2

⁹ <https://analytics.google.com>

Figure 10: Google Analytics 2/2

Updated website “traffic” and more detailed analytics can be presented in future deliverables related to “Dissemination & Communication plans and activities”, D6.1, D6.2 and D6.3, that will be submitted on M5, 20 and 36 respectively.

3.4 Website Administration

This chapter describes the administration site of the 5G-ROUTES website. The website has been built using the WordPress¹⁰ (version 5.4.2). WordPress is a web-based software widely used for website designs with emphasis on accessibility, performance, security, and ease of use. WordPress is GDPR compliant and offers a large database of plugins to be used which are always updated with new trends and they are user friendly. The WordPress platform is hosted by Bluehost¹¹, a web hosting solutions company. Bluehost always installs the latest version of WordPress so all the recent features are available in 5G-ROUTES website.

Figure 11 below, illustrates the welcome/main page that is displayed once the administrator user login to the WordPress. The navigation menu (on the left of the website) helps the user easily navigate through the different categories of the 5G-ROUTES project website.

¹⁰ <https://wordpress.org/about/>

¹¹ <https://www.bluehost.com/about>

Figure 11: WordPress – Main page

Using the WordPress, the administrator can create a new page, rename or delete an existing page along with the option to change the content of an existing page. The administrator may also see and edit the ‘Menu items’ and ‘Menu Structure’. Indicative screenshots of the above-mentioned functionalities are presented in the following Figures 12 and 13.

Figure 12: WordPress – Edit Website/Page Content

Figure 13: WordPress – Edit Menu

4 Project's Social Media Channels

This Chapter describes the 5G-ROUTES social media accounts in LinkedIn, Twitter and YouTube which are (along with the website) part of the dissemination activities undertaken for this project.

The 5G-ROUTES LinkedIn page <https://www.linkedin.com/company/5g-routes-project/> was created during the first month of the Project. The LinkedIn page provides a large dissemination channel where executives in the field of 5G technology connect. This channel will be used to massively disseminate project facts, results, links to work, links to events etc., including all major project steps, meetings and major outcomes. During the preparation of this report, the group was already counting a number of members, and a number of announcements/posts (i.e. Kick off Meeting). A sample screenshot from the LinkedIn page is presented in the following Figure.

5G-ROUTES Project
Research · Brussels · 27 followers

[Visit website](#)

Overview

5G-ROUTES is a 5G-PPP Phase 3 project whose aim is to validate through robust evidence the latest 5G features and 3GPP specifications (R.16 & R.17) of Connected and Automated Mobility (CAM) under realistic conditions. In particular, it will conduct advanced large-scale field trials of most representative CAM applications to demonstrate seamless functionality across a prominent 5G cross-border corridor (Via Baltica-North), traversing Latvia, Estonia and Finland. This will help to boost confidence and accelerate the deployment of 5G-based interoperable CAM ecosystems and services throughout Europe.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under grant agreement No 951867.

Website	https://www.5g-routes.eu/
Industry	Research
Company size	51-200 employees
Type	Partnership
Founded	2020

Figure 14: 5G-ROUTES LinkedIn Channel - About

Figure 15: 5G-ROUTES LinkedIn Channel - Posts

The 5G-ROUTES Twitter account has also been created since the very early stages of the project (M1) and will be used for dissemination purposes like the LinkedIn group. The objective here is to use it not only as a mass-dissemination tool but also as a way of providing links between the project partners and related research, stakeholders or potential 5G-ROUTES up-takers. Twitter will be also maintained throughout the whole project duration. The 5G-ROUTES Twitter account can be found in the following link <https://twitter.com/5gRoutes>. A

sample screenshot from the Twitter account is presented in the following Figure. During the preparation of this report, the channel had already a number of followers and tweets (i.e. Kick off Meeting).

Figure 16: 5G-ROUTES Twitter Channel

Moreover, a YouTube channel has already been created and will be used for posting videos related to the project and its outputs. 5G-ROUTES YouTube channel is accessible via the following link <https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCEvuQqzJPpMYQdQPvQ1dD4g/>. A snapshot of 5G-ROUTES YouTube channel is presented in the following Figure.

Figure 17: 5G-ROUTES YouTube Channel

It was decided by the Consortium that Facebook is not the most appropriate social media channel for disseminating the project, that's why we will not have it as part of the dissemination activities. Instead of Facebook, an additional dissemination channel has been utilised, called "Knowledge Base". As part of this activity, we are leveraging the interactive web-based Knowledge Base¹² initially implemented under SELIS¹³ project, extending its functionality to support 5 more H2020 project's and their dissemination activities. The Knowledge Base will contain a large library of project's activities and outputs (public deliverables, publications) along with selective articles related to the project concept. The Knowledge Base will be formulated and structured based on the project's concept following the standards of a web portal and utilizing the latest technology in order to provide to the user/visitor a rich content information through a cross-browser and multi-device compatibility.

Throughout the lifecycle of the project, the users will have the ability to continuously enrich the content of the Knowledge Base, providing a large base and a one-stop info source for all players in the 5G-ROUTES ecosystem. The content updating process will be fully moderated, meaning that the content updates will be published upon administrator's (Dissemination Manager) reviewing and approval.

¹² <https://www.knowledgeportalcenter.com/>

¹³ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/690588>

Knowledge Base will continue disseminating project results even beyond the project completion. A screenshot of the Knowledge Base website is presented in the following Figure, showing a way to access the related environment with dissemination material for the 5G-ROUTES project.

Figure 18: Knowledge Base

5 Conclusions and Next Actions

This document describes the project’s website and social media accounts which are considered as the online 5G-ROUTES Project presence. Links to access the website but also the LinkedIn and Twitter accounts are also provided within the document. How the administration of the website is performed is also described along with the methodology behind the design and development of the website as such and some statistical reports on website traffic (extracted from Google Analytics).

This deliverable is part of T6.1 “Dissemination and Communication Activities” performed under WP6 “Dissemination, Communications and scale-up” For that reason, the content of the website and social media accounts will be continuously updated with dissemination material until the completion of the Project.

According to the “Dissemination and communication outcome, metrics and targets” (Table 2.7 of DoA), the Project’s website should have been online by M1, which has been achieved. Then, the target is to have 1000 unique visitors by M12 and 2000 by M36.

Regarding the Social media, the targets are the following:

- LinkedIn page followers: more than 200;
- Twitter followers: more than 200;
- Re-Tweets: more than 200.

Annex 1: Project's Website Page Screenshots

Concept and Methodology

The 5G-ROUTES technical approach is based on a modular architecture in which the various 5G CAM technological enablers are integrated via open interfaces and APIs.

[Read more](#)

Work Plan

The project is organised in six (6) Work Packages (WPs) that correspond to the project's objectives, coordinated by project management activities (WP7).

[Read more](#)

Objectives

Innovative use cases defined with key industry experts: To develop innovative and commercially exploitable CAM use cases for automotive, railway and maritime sectors within the cross-border context.

[Read more](#)

Consortium

Structure of the Project Management Board and an Introduction of the Project Consortium

[Read more](#)

CAM Trials

The CAM pilots will allow to better understand the roles, relations and responsibilities of market players within the CAM ecosystem.

[Read more](#)

5G-ROUTES is a 5G-PPP Phase 3 project whose aim is to validate through robust evidence the latest 5G features and 3GPP specifications (R.16 & R.17) of Connected and Automated Mobility (CAM) under realistic conditions. In particular, it will conduct advanced large-scale field trials of most representative CAM applications to demonstrate seamless functionality across a prominent 5G cross-border corridor (Via Baltica-North), traversing Latvia, Estonia and Finland.

Site Links

- [Home](#)
- [About](#)
- [Dissemination & Communication](#)
- [News & Events](#)
- [Contact Us](#)

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Designed and Developed by eBOS Technologies

Concept and Methodology

To conduct advanced field trials of most representative and innovative CAM applications seamlessly functioning across a designated 5G cross-border corridor ('Via Baltica-North') spanning across 3 EU member states borders (Latvia-Estonia-Finland) in order to validate the latest 5G features and 3GPP specifications under realistic conditions, so as to accelerate the widespread deployment of 5G E2E interoperable CAM ecosystems and services in digitised motorways, railways and shipways throughout Europe.

The 5G-ROUTES conceptual approach has been carefully structured along the following 3 pillars:

1. Formulating and validating a wide set of innovative, complementary and meaningful advanced use cases directly relevant to CAM (also aligned with 3GPP V2X Phase 3) and cross-border mobility across the 'Via Baltica-North' 5G corridor (traversing Latvia, Estonia and Finland). In particular, validating the technical (i.e. network-level) and service-level performance conforming to >150 target 5G KPIs specified per use case (Table 1.6).
2. Providing the technological enablers for facilitating the execution of the field trials, and in particular:
 - Integrating in cross-border CAM field trials a set of innovative enabling technologies, such as AI-based network slicing and optimisation, AI-based distributed MEC for CAM services, AI-based 5G radio interface for innovative shared spectrum usage for CAM services, AI-based positioning enhancements for V2X, cross domain integration fabric for multi-domain interaction and service roaming, combined with commercial 5G base stations and other CAM complementary technologies, such as satellite 5G connectivity for serving remote areas, vehicular On-Board Units (OBUs), IEEE 802.11p in vehicles and FRMCS in railways.
 - Leveraging the KPI visualisation system the 5G-SOLUTIONS project and extending its functionality to incorporate the CAM use cases, thus enabling the parallel execution of use cases, automating the analysis and presentation of the results obtained from the trials and presenting them through an intuitive user-friendly dashboard in near-real time.
3. Aligning the implementation roadmap of 5G-ROUTES roadmap with the latest 3GPP standardisation releases.

The 5G-ROUTES technical approach is based on a modular architecture in which the various 5G CAM technological enablers are integrated via open interfaces and APIs. These enablers will facilitate the measurement and visualisation of 5G network and service-level KPIs of the use cases, in parallel, and in near real-time whilst exercised in the field, as well as benchmarking and access from multiple locations.

The high-level architectural approach of 5G-ROUTES (Figure above), and its constituent elements are based on the latter objectives. Each MNO will deploy an independent 3GPP-based 5G network (following the forthcoming R.16 & R.17 releases) and an ETSI compliant NFV Cloud solution with a Management and Orchestration stack at the core. The latter will support automatic resource scaling based on the workload, by leveraging ETSI compliant orchestration solutions. This provides the necessary flexibility for the system to adapt to new interfaces, data sources, GDPR compliant data processing, machine learning and other CAM and network services that may be required during the interfacing with the 5G infrastructure and CAM ecosystem.

Both, the ETSI OSM and the ATOS Canopy Hybrid Cloud Orchestration solutions will be considered, as they offer compatibility with OpenStack as well as with Public Clouds, simplifying interoperability and CAM service roaming. The latter also provides access to Public Clouds' AI engines. Furthermore, a MEC solution, in line with the ETSI GR MEC 022 specifications for V2X support and ETSI GR MEC 017 specifications⁵ will be deployed at the network Edge, to allow the re-use of ETSI NFV MANO functionality in both the Edge and Core clouds. CAM functions will be implemented as a collection of Core and Edge Services (or Virtual Network Functions – VNFs) and orchestrated by the NFV Orchestrator (NFVO) and the Mobile Edge Application Orchestrator (MEAO), respectively.

Finally, highspeed and low latency satellite links, based on a Low Earth Orbit (LEO) constellation, will provide 5G backhauling in underserved areas. The main elements of the architecture are:

A 5G deployment with dynamic Network Slicing support.

The 5G-ROUTES networks will be validated over the emerging 3GPP releases R.16 & R.17, for the 5G RAN and Core. Furthermore, they will support zero-touch network slice management mechanisms through AI-based approaches that dynamically allocate resources by predicting the traffic patterns and user mobility behavior in real-time. This will help satisfy the demanding CAM service SLAs in vehicular use cases, supporting user roaming across borders.

A distributed Mobile Edge Computing (MEC)

A distributed Mobile Edge Computing (MEC) solution based on Ericsson's Edge NFVI platform will be deployed in the 5G-ROUTES NFV environment. MEC is an effective approach in scenarios where computing capacity is required at the edge of the network and its role is pivotal to meeting the stringent requirements of eMBB and URLLC service classes. 5G-ROUTES will leverage Ericsson's mature and powerful MEAO to distribute and continuously roam CAM services across all edge sites and across borders, taking into account mobility patterns

An integrated terrestrial-satellite 5G connectivity

An integrated terrestrial-satellite 5G connectivity realised through dual connectivity (terrestrial – SatCom) providing service continuity throughout cross-border and uncovered areas. This continuity is enabled by a seamless handover between 3GPP (5G terrestrial) and (un)trusted non-3GPP (satellite) accesses as discussed in the framework of 3GPP releases R.16 & R.17. This feature implies interfacing satellite operator traffic flow with the MNO core network considering control mechanism for handover triggering. This will provide a unique value proposition that extends beyond standalone backup 5G satellite connectivity.

An inter-domain integration fabric

An inter-domain integration fabric, compatible with ETSI ZSM specifications, which will facilitate cross-domain service management and CAM service roaming. While cloud and network resources in each domain will be managed independently by the MNO, cross-domain coordination is still needed such that the CAM services work seamlessly across borders. The integration fabric will allow management services, such as the VNF Manager, from different domains to publish and subscribe via appropriate APIs, facilitating real-time exchange of data and analytics. Hence, VNF Management & Orchestration decisions and SLAs remain consistent across MNOs.

Tenant Web Portal

The use of the Tenant Web Portal is considered as an important element to 5G-ROUTES to automate and accelerate the execution of the use cases running in parallel, as well as the analysis, benchmarking and presentation of the technical KPIs from cross-border field trials, whilst being in the field, by using big-data graph analytics and cloud-computing for rapid and automated processing of the vast amount of data obtained from the trials. The portal interacts with the 5G enabling technologies through relevant open standards intent-based APIs. To realise the portal, the KPI visualisation system developed as part of 5GSOLUTIONS project will be leveraged and extended so as to cover multi-tenancy in the cloud, the cross-border context and the additional KPIs in each of the use cases.

Work Plan

Overall Structure of the Work Plan

The project is organised in six (6) Work Packages (WPs) that correspond to the project’s objectives, coordinated by project management activities (WP7). Each WP is led by a project partner particularly experienced in the corresponding area, so as to ensure the best practice and work efficiency. Figure below summarises the project structure, illustrating the relationships between WPs, organised in 3 main groups:

- **Providing Technical Foundations (WP1-WP3):** Design, implement 5G-ROUTES technological enablers and setup the 5G CAM infrastructure to facilitate large-scale CAM service field trial validation.
- **Enabling Industrial Acceptance (WP4):** Validate and transform core technical, service and business results to a state suitable for deployment in an operational environment.
- **Impact maximisation (WP5-WP6):** Carry out dissemination, communication, exploitation, standardisation and capacity building activities

Objectives

5G-ROUTES Overall Project Objective:

To conduct advanced field trials of most representative and innovative CAM applications seamlessly functioning across a designated 5G cross-border corridor ('Via Baltica-North') spanning across 3 EU member states borders (Latvia-Estonia-Finland) in order to validate the latest 5G features and 3GPP specifications under realistic conditions, so as to accelerate the widespread deployment of 5G E2E interoperable CAM ecosystems and services in digitised motorways, railways and shipways throughout Europe.

To achieve the overall project's objective, the following eight (8) key interdisciplinary implementation objectives have been defined, which are SMART, i.e. Specific, Measurable, Attainable, Realistic and Time bound.

Objective 1

Innovative use cases defined with key industry experts: To develop innovative and commercially exploitable CAM use cases for automotive, railway and maritime sectors within the cross-border context.

Objective 2

Requirements analysis elaboration: To analyse the technical and business requirements for the use cases to enable extensive large-scale CAM field trials in the 'Via Baltica-North' 5G corridor.

Objective 3

Enabling Technologies: To advance and optimise the enabling technologies using AI for the reliable, seamless and uninterrupted delivery of interoperable CAM services across borders.

Objective 4

Infrastructure development, integration & setup: To leverage and upgrade key assets from previous results and commercial products; to integrate the technological enablers in an end-to-end CAM ecosystem, to setup the 5G corridor and to facilitate lab and large-scale field trial validation.

Objective 5

Field Trials Validation: To demonstrate the potential and the user value in advanced CAM deployments at cross-border areas, by characterising and optimising 5G technologies at both lab tests and large-scale trials, so as to validate applicable standards and key target KPIs thus boosting the confidence for wide adoption of interoperable CAM services in Europe.

Objective 6

Exploitation & Innovation Management: To develop and validate the business models of advanced CAM use cases that can be offered on top of existing services in a multi cross-border 5G operator environment, demonstrating benefits from potential operational cost reductions and new revenue generation streams. To protect EU IP and ensure long-term economic sustainability.

Objective 7

Contribution to Standardisation: To identify and validate applicable standards as well as provide rationalised contribution to key standardisation bodies so as to sustain standardisation in the telecom and automotive sectors within the CAM context. To promote a proactive and joint approach through consortium partners, members of pre-standardisation bodies and fora (e.g. 5G-PPP, 5G-AA, IETF, NGMN, UIC) and Standards Developing Organisations (SDOs), such as 3GPP, ITU-T, IEEE SA, ETSI, CEN, ISO, ONF suggesting specific planning actions and contributions for the 2nd and subsequent phases of 5G standardisation, so that they can be taken into consideration in future releases (e.g. 3GPP Rel.18) to maximise impact on standardisation.

Objective 8

Scale-up: To ensure long-term success through wide dissemination of the project's results; to exploit synergies with other 5G-PPP projects and 5G CAM initiatives; to actively contribute to the 5G Action Plan strategic initiative with results from 5G technologies validation in CAM trials for the benefit of the European 5G, automotive, railways, maritime, transport & logistics industries, the university education and training of young and other professionals.

Project Coordinator

Consortium

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CAM Trials

Innovative use cases in CAM pilots

The CAM pilots will allow to better understand the roles, relations and responsibilities of market players within the CAM ecosystem.

For all use cases, the network, service-level and business perspectives will be validated against pre-defined target KPI values during the trials. The differentiation and correlation of the KPIs is as follows:

- The network KPIs, which are related to the 5G communication network, describe the requirements for information exchange between road users and between the users on the move and the infrastructure. Such KPIs include throughput, mobility, latency, connection density, reliability, positioning accuracy, handover time, etc.
- The service-level KPIs, which are related to CAM services, describe the behaviour of the services for the users and goods on the move, e.g. vehicle drivers, vehicle, railway operation, railway and maritime passengers, cargo, etc. Such KPIs include service continuity, service interruption time, Quality of Experience (QoE), etc.
- The business KPIs, which are related to the business perspective of the CAM services, and include cost/benefit analysis to justify investment and commercial benefits, revenue generation models, reduced OPEX, CAPEX, etc.

Cross-border Use Cases

Use Case Category (UCC) 1: Automated Cooperative Driving

Automated driving involves an increased level of automation of the vehicle functions and a reduction of the involvement of the driver. However, to achieve the vision of fully autonomous driving, several key enabling capabilities need to be implemented both in vehicles as well as in communication networks. 5G connectivity associated with V2X communication functions, dynamic mapping, accurate positioning, edge-based and AI solutions are expected to overcome most of these challenges by providing more visibility and cooperative decisionmaking mechanisms through communication with the infrastructure and surrounding vehicles. Therefore, MEC-enabled 5G RAN nodes, enhanced with AI, continue to gain more intelligence and capacity to support evolving network demands and superior network experiences that are necessary for the realisation of highly automated cooperating driving.

Use Case 1.1: Dynamic vehicles platooning to enable vehicles to dynamically form a group travelling together and very close to each other

Use Case 1.2: Cooperative lane change to perform joint maneuver decisions and coordinate driving trajectories amongst a group of vehicles, in order to enhance the safety and help the vehicles getting through difficult traffic situations.

Use Case 1.3: See-Through view for safe automated to provide enhanced visibility of road awareness for safe automated overtake in order to prevent catastrophic head-on collisions during an automated overtake manoeuvre.

Use Case Category (UCC) 2: Awareness Driving

The primary objective of UCC2 is to enable the reliable exchange of road traffic status data, such as enhanced real-time traffic video feeds and control in complex intersections via V2X communication, e.g. the position, speed, driving trajectories, VRUs, so as to enable safe passing and avoiding collisions as well as providing user comfort in traffic jams during automated driving.

Use Case 2.1: Real-time traffic information and cooperative intersection collision control to provide enhanced real-time traffic visual monitoring and control of intersection traffic for cooperative automated driving for safe passing and avoiding collisions with other vehicles and VRUs.

Use Case 2.2: Traffic jam chauffeur to provide automated driving functionality in traffic jams for increased user comfort and satisfaction.

Use Case Category (UCC) 3: Sensing Driving

The primary objective of UCC3 is to enable connected vehicles to share observations gained by sensors, and advanced environmental information, to gain enhanced situational awareness especially for the presence of noncommunicating VRUs who are beyond the direct line of sight of drivers, as well as to create a preventive maintenance framework with predictive analytics, to enable long-term maintenance and repair services throughout the lifetime of vehicles. In this way, other traffic participants may be warned in advanced against dangers they could not perceive themselves, whilst protecting VRUs in different traffic situations.

Use Case 3.1: Sensor info sharing for cooperative situation awareness to allow connected vehicles travelling in close proximity to each other in motorways, to form part of a group to exchange sensor data, collaborate and thus guarantee the safety for all involved nearby vehicles.

Use Case 3.2: Connected maintenance to create a preventive maintenance framework and a new maintenance business model through which the data collected from the sensors, in combination with predictive analytics, enable long-term maintenance and repair services thus enabling customer support to follow the vehicles owners throughout the lifetime of their vehicles.

Use Case 3.3: Vulnerable Road User (VRU) Collision Avoidance to extend safety protection for VRU by enabling reliable interaction between active vehicle and surrounding passive VRUs.

Use Case Category (UCC) 4: Uninterrupted infotainment passenger services on the go

The objective of UCC4 is to allow and enable multimodal passengers to exploit the high-performance capabilities of 5G networks while on-route and when crossing EU member states borders. The expectations are for the same seamless user experience everywhere, both for productivity purposes and for entertainment. In this regard, 40-50 end-users, participants in the following use cases will be provided with 5G enabled smartphones equipped with relevant applications (as described below) so that they can test the experience and provide us with feedback together with QoE evaluation, also helping us in validating the business potential of the use cases.

Use Case 4.1: 360o Immersive multi-user gaming on the go to provide uninterrupted 360o immersive multi-user gaming experience to validate how business continuity can be achieved across borders and across different means of transport (i.e. automotive, railways and maritime)

Use Case 4.2: 3D real-time virtual collaboration on the move to provide seamless uninterrupted 3D virtual collaboration experience to validate how business continuity can be achieved across borders and across different means of transport (i.e. automotive, railways and maritime).

Use Case Category (UCC) 5: Multimodal services

FRMCS as the successor of GSM-R is a key enabler for rail transport digitalisation. Furthermore, it is equally important to have uninterrupted and seamless service delivery to passengers and visibility of tracked goods through different modes of transport, such as for example, when changing vehicles or trains to onboard ship liners for journey continuation. In this regard, the QoE for the service should remain unaltered irrespective of the change of transport means, the 5G network provider (terrestrial and/or satellite) and country.

Use Case 5.1: Goods tracking visibility in multimodal cross border logistics to provide seamless tracking of massive amount of goods to validate how business continuity can be achieved across borders, across different means of transport (i.e. automotive, railways and maritime) massive Machine Type of Communications (mMTC) and across terrestrial and satellite 5G operators.

Use Case 5.2: 5G-based Proactive and Multimodal Management of Passengers and Freight to provide proactive and multimodal management of passengers and freight when crossing borders including across terrestrial and satellite 5G operators.

Use Case 5.3: FRMCS telemetry operation to improve service availability and performance for telemetry operation of railways through FRMCS.

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5G-ROUTES is a 5G-PPP Phase 3 project whose aim is to validate through robust evidence the latest 5G features and 3GPP specifications (R.16 & R.17) of Connected and Automated Mobility (CAM) under realistic conditions. In particular, it will conduct advanced large-scale field trials of most representative CAM applications to demonstrate seamless functionality across a prominent 5G cross-border corridor (Via Baltica-North), traversing Latvia, Estonia and Finland.

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Public Deliverables

D#	Deliverable Name	WP#	Lead Participant	Type	Delivery Month
D1.1	Use cases, scenarios, specifications and target KPIs for 5G for CAM v1.0	WP1	ADS	R	4
D1.2	Use cases, scenarios, specifications and target KPIs for 5G for CAM v2.0	WP1	ADS	R	23
D1.3	Report on 5G-ROUTES CAM deployment plan and longer-term deployment strategies v1.0	WP1	LMT	R	2
D1.4	Report on 5G-ROUTES CAM deployment plan and longer-term deployment strategies v2.0	WP1	LMT	R	23
D1.5	Methodologies for cross-border collaboration and validation of 5G features for CAM v1.0	WP1	TELIA	R	4
D1.6	Methodologies for cross-border collaboration and validation of 5G features for CAM v2.0	WP1	TELIA	R	24
D1.7	Testing framework for the technological and business validation and benchmarking of the results v1.0	WP1	VTT	R	3
D1.8	Testing framework for the technological and business validation and benchmarking of the results v2.0	WP1	VTT	R	24
D2.9	Report on integration and testing of technological enablers for CAM v1.0	WP2	ATOS	R	9
D2.10	Report on integration and testing of technological enablers for CAM v2.0	WP2	ATOS	R	27
D3.1	Report on infrastructure setup and integration of the 5G CAM ecosystem v1.0	WP3	TELIA	R	9
D3.2	Report on infrastructure setup and integration of the 5G CAM ecosystem v2.0	WP3	TELIA	R	28
D3.3	Report on CAM infrastructure setup in vehicles and in railways v1.0	WP3		R	9
D3.4	Report on CAM infrastructure setup in vehicles and in railways v2.0	WP3		R	26
D3.5	Report on integration of technological enablers with MNOs 5G infrastructure and incremental upgrades v1.0	WP3	LMT	R	12
D3.6	Report on integration of technological enablers with MNOs 5G infrastructure and incremental upgrades v2.0	WP3	LMT	R	19
D3.7	Report on integration of technological enablers with MNOs 5G infrastructure and incremental upgrades Final Version	WP3	LMT	R	28
D3.8	Report on lab trials findings and field trials operational readiness v1.0	WP3	VTT	R	13
D3.9	Report on lab trials findings and field trials operational readiness v2.0	WP3	VTT	R	19
D3.10	Report on lab trials findings and field trials operational readiness Final Version	WP3	VTT	R	28
D4.1	Field trials planning, setup and operational management handbook v1.0	WP4	BRA	R	13
D4.2	Field trials planning, setup and operational management handbook v2.0	WP4	BRA	R	33
D4.3	5G CAM field trials v1.0	WP4	EEE	DEM	20

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